

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PRACTICAL ADAPTATION OF THE SYSTEM FOR ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGISTICS ACTIVITIES. DEVELOPMENT OF AN ECONOMIC STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

The article is concerned with developing a practical methodology for adapting the system for assessing the effectiveness of innovative development of logistics activities. Particular attention is paid to road transport enterprises that face growing challenges in the context of globalisation and the transition to sustainable development. The paper substantiates the importance of using the latest digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data and automation, to optimise logistics processes and increase competitiveness. The paper proposes an economic strategy that takes into account innovative solutions and contributes to sustainable development, in particular by increasing energy efficiency and reducing the negative impact on the environment. The results of the study demonstrate how the practical application of game theory, in particular Nash equilibrium, can contribute to optimal decision-making in logistics activities.

Keywords: logistics, innovation, economic strategy, sustainable development, digital technologies.

Relevance of the topic (Introduction)

Modern logistics systems are one of the key elements of the economy that ensure the efficient operation of supply chains and transport systems. The development of innovative technologies, such as process automation, digital platforms, artificial intelligence and the use of big data, is significantly changing the way logistics is managed. The introduction of these innovations is an important factor in improving the efficiency of logistics operations, reducing costs and increasing the competitiveness of companies in the market. However, in order to ensure sustainable development and maximise economic benefits, a system for evaluating the effectiveness of innovative logistics solutions is needed. An economic strategy based on such assessments will allow companies to optimise their resources and processes. The relevance of the topic lies in the need for practical adaptation of such evaluation systems for real enterprises, which will allow for more effective management of innovative development in logistics.

Logistics has become an integral part of economic systems, encompassing both internal company processes and external supply chains. Innovations in logistics not only reduce costs and lead times, but also improve customer service, reduce greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to sustainable development. In this regard, there is a need for effective tools to assess the effectiveness of innovative solutions. The urgency of this problem lies in the fact that today most companies use general indicators to assess their performance, which do not take into account the specifics of innovative changes and their long-term impact on the company's economy.

The use of innovation performance measurement systems will allow companies to formulate more accurate economic strategies that take into account the potential of innovation and its impact on economic sustainability and competitiveness. This is especially important in the context of globalisation and growing

demands for environmental sustainability, which makes the topic of this article particularly relevant.

Ukrainian researchers have also paid attention to the economic efficiency of innovations in logistics. For example, Bondarenko S.V. analyses the economic efficiency of logistics solutions at motor transport enterprises, focusing on the importance of innovations for reducing costs and increasing the productivity of enterprises [1].

The study of Ustilovska A. and others concerns the introduction of modern HR technologies to improve the efficiency of transport logistics processes in the construction industry, in particular in multimodal transport of construction materials [2].

However, existing scientific developments and methods do not always allow for full consideration of key performance indicators of innovations and their impact on the sustainable development of enterprises, which complicates the development of appropriate economic strategies. This necessitates the creation of tools that would provide a comprehensive assessment of innovations and help improve the management of innovation processes at motor transport enterprises.

The unresolved problem is that no effective and universal methodology for adapting the system for assessing the effectiveness of innovative development of logistics activities of motor transport enterprises has been developed to date.

Purpose of the article

The aim of this article is to develop a methodology for practical adaptation of the system for assessing the effectiveness of innovative development of logistics activities of motor transport enterprises. It involves analysing key indicators of efficiency of innovations, their impact on the sustainable development of enterprises, as well as formulating recommendations for the development of economic strategies that take these indicators into account.

The main part

The 21st century can be safely identified with such concepts as innovative development, evaluation of the effectiveness of innovations, and logistics activities. Depending on the historical era, the terminological apparatus of the above-mentioned concepts evolved and changed under the influence of the trends of the respective periods.

Kenneth B. Kahn, Ph.D., views innovation as three distinct things: innovation is an outcome, innovation is a process, and innovation is a mindset. Innovation as an outcome emphasizes what products strive for, including product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, business model innovation, supply chain innovation, and organizational innovation. Innovation as a process is concerned with how innovation should be organized so that results can be realized; this includes the overall innovation process and the new product development process. Innovation as a mindset refers to the internalization of innovation by individual members of an organization, where innovation is instilled and rooted, along with the creation of a supportive organizational culture that allows innovation to flourish. Such an understanding defines the necessary elements, considerations and vernacular surrounding the term so that the best decisions can be made, thereby enabling innovation and having a greater propensity for success [3].

Peter Ferdinand Drucker, an American scientist of Austrian origin, believes that innovation is nothing more than a specific tool of entrepreneurs, a means by which they use change as an opportunity for another business or another service [4].

According to the author, **innovation** is a fairly complex economic category, which is the object of research and essentially means the creation of new value to meet economic needs and obtain noticeably positive results of activity. This is a significant improvement of an already existing or introduction of a new product / service / process / method of doing business. This is not only the creation of new, better ones, but also the development and improvement of existing business models and new ideas.

Evolution and growth are associated with the concept of development. This is a fairly old, but comprehensive concept. Development can be physical, mental, economic, social, innovative, etc. And the more developed the nation, the more emphasis the country places on improving various processes, both economic and social. Development is always about expanding opportunities and using them in different ways.

Mohamed Rabie in his work "A Theory of Sustainable Sociocultural and Economic Development" concludes that development is primarily an economic concept that has positive connotations; it involves the application of certain economic and technical measures to use available resources to stimulate economic growth and improve people's quality of life [5].

Vinichenko O.M. It characterizes development as a system component, which is considered as certain connections of a set of other components of the system, clarifying that this is a property of system objects that

determines the adaptation of this system to the conditions of the external and internal environment in order to ensure the further functioning of the system [6].

Considering this concept as an action aimed at moving underdeveloped countries from a state of economic backwardness to a dynamic state, the author considers **development** as a peculiar process by which societies move through a fundamental, complete structural transition from one state to another, using the necessary approaches for economic and social growth, improving the skills, knowledge and abilities of participants in a specific process.

Based on the above, the author comes to the conclusion that **innovative development** is a process of transition to a new, higher and more desirable level in accordance with the target tasks in one period of time compared to the previous one, in which subjects strategically expand their activities, systematically introducing new tools and processes as stages of the evolution of their culture.

The essence of innovative development is as follows: it improves social life, minimizes the negative impact on the environment, reduces hunger, solves problems in education, makes society safer and allows people to live productive lives. This is one of the main conditions for solving the current economic and social problems of modern society, a complex process associated with stages and developments - from the restoration of infrastructure to the rebalancing of societies - which require long-term planning, large-scale investments and, in general, stability and endurance.

To compete in this ever-changing environment, companies must create new products, services and processes; to dominate, they must embrace innovation as a way of corporate life, evaluating innovative development in terms of performance.

In the scientific literature, the concept of effectiveness is not considered lively enough. Instead, the concept of efficiency is often discussed. Most scientists identify the understanding of effectiveness and efficiency. Although both terms focus on achieving success, they nevertheless have different important structural components.

Having considered the comparative characteristics of the conceptual apparatus of efficiency and effectiveness given by scientist Peter Drucker, it becomes obvious that effectiveness is a much broader concept than efficiency [7]. Because effectiveness focuses on the end results, determining the rationale for achieving a specific goal, taking into account long-term goals. And efficiency is aimed at obtaining a mostly financial effect.

The author offers the following definition of the concept of **"effectiveness"** as the direction of efforts, coordination of strategies to achieve the set goals, which provide tangible and effective results for the organization, greater probability of success and confidence in obtaining competitive advantages. Where the result itself is an actual indicator relative to the planned one.

In the conditions of a market economy, the concept of effectiveness is a priority component, both in the activities of an individual enterprise and in the state

economic policy as a whole, where innovative development leads to socio-economic and environmental growth.

Assessing the effectiveness of innovative development is an indispensable condition for ensuring structural changes and obtaining reliable evidence that the adopted decisions will have the planned positive effect. Assessing makes it possible not only to identify shortcomings, but also to form a plan of strategic decisions aimed at improving business processes, strengthening positions, increasing effectiveness and ensuring a positive impact on financial results.

Linda J. Morra Imas defines assessing as the process of determining the value or value of an action, policy, or program. It is the most systematic and objective and refers to a planned, ongoing or completed intervention [8].

Based on the fact that this process of determining the value makes it possible to obtain a full justification of economic decisions in modern conditions, the author offers his own definition of the concept of "**assessing**" as a kind of measurement of goals, with the aim of timely correction of actions in order to achieve the expected results.

Thus, according to the author, **assessing the effectiveness** is the measurement of planned goals that produce tangible, effective results using methodological approaches.

Since the modern economy is characterized by high risks, such as inflation, the instability of many social, economic and political conditions, the qualitative diagnosis of innovative processes is increasingly necessary. The basis of forming strategic decisions regarding the introduction of innovations is the method of evaluating the effectiveness of innovative development. The need for this tool lies in the ability to provide evidentiary information about the effectiveness of planned actions, after assessing possible risks, and to meet the modern requirements for the development of innovative activities.

The methodology for assessing the effectiveness of innovative development should consist of indicators that characterize the innovative potential of the enterprise, provide the possibility of conducting an analysis of the comparison of characteristics and indicators, harmonizing them with the existing reporting at the enterprise, and consist mainly of the following stages:

- assessing of the external environment (takes place by monitoring such external factors as legislative changes, technological progress, market competition, changes in consumer needs);
- Monitoring of the internal environment (takes place with the help of assessment of such internal factors as financial condition, human resources, scientific research complex, infrastructure capital);
- Development of a strategy for increasing the innovative potential of the company (occurs due to the concentration of scientific, production and financial potential);
- Assessing of the effectiveness of the innovation project (it takes place with the help of obtaining analytical data from the implementation of innovations, construction of comparative characteristics of the impact of

the company's activities on the level of quality, success and financial indicators);

- Risk analysis (takes place due to identification of probable innovation risks, assessment of risk consequences and past failures, formation of anti-crisis measures). This stage is quite important for making cost-effective management decisions [Summarized by the author based on sources 9-11].

The use of assessing methods allows interested parties to receive objective assessments and make informed decisions about improving their activities and achieving their goals, take into account influencing factors, and determine the level of the company's readiness for improvements.

In the 21st century, innovations have become the most important indicator of the level of economic growth of the country, since their successful implementation ensures a qualitative increase in the effectiveness of all stages of production required by the market. Logistics, accumulating such production cycles as pre-production, production and post-production activities, acts as a kind of indicator in the analysis of indicators of the implementation of innovative technologies in practice.

The concept of logistics itself has been studied by scientists for more than a decade. Thus, in the textbook edited by M.A. Nefiodov, scientists define logistics as the science of planning, control and management of transportation, warehousing and other material and non-material operations carried out in the process of bringing raw materials and materials to the production enterprise, in-plant processing of raw materials, materials and semi-finished products, bringing finished products to the consumer in accordance with the requirements the latter, as well as transmission, storage and processing of relevant information [12].

Logistics is the science of integrated management of material and related flows in various (including economic) systems. This understanding is given by a group of scientists in their article "Main characteristics of the concept of logistics and supply chain management systems" [13].

In the manual edited by N.M. Tyurina, logistics is defined as the science of integrated management of material and related flows in various (including economic) systems [14].

Understanding **logistics** as a process of planning and carrying out effective transportation and storage of goods, the author defines this concept as a science aimed at solving issues of successful management of various types of material, energy, financial, resource and information flows, including the stages of planning, procurement, transportation and storage of goods, satisfying the needs of the end user as efficiently as possible.

Managing the flow of goods, energy, information and other resources from the point of origin to the point of consumption in today's globalized world, logistics activities are the backbone of any organization. Today, this type of activity is a vivid example of innovative development.

In turn, after analyzing the definitions of explanatory dictionaries [15,16], the author understands the

concept of "**activity**" as meaningful human activity to achieve a certain goal.

According to the author, **logistics activity** is a coordinated set of actions aimed at ensuring the coordinated and effective execution of all stages of the logistics process.

Logistics today needs the formation of concepts that will help to cope with the high level of requirements, needs flexible logistics strategies, so innovations in this field and support of transport enterprises are absolutely necessary. In recent decades, the supply chain industry has experienced an accelerated pace of transformation. Expanding the possibilities of transmotion initiatives, digital functions are being developed at transport enterprises, service is improved, sustainability and transparency are increased.

In order to understand the essence of the concept of a transport enterprise, let's consider the definition of two concepts separately.

Transport is one of the most important branches of public production and is designed to meet the needs of the population and public production in transportation in accordance with the Law of Ukraine On Transport [17].

The explanatory dictionary defines the concept of an enterprise as an independent economic and administrative self-financed unit - a legal entity that performs production, commercial, trade and other functions, provides services for the purpose of obtaining profit [18].

The author notes that if **transport** is the process of moving people or goods from one place to another, and an **enterprise** is any entity engaged in economic activity regardless of its legal form, then a **transport enterprise** is an organization whose main activity is the movement of goods to their destination.

The formation of an effective organizational structure, which leads to the effective implementation of the logistics approach in the practical activities of enterprises, is the result of innovations in the logistics management system, where there is a coordinated movement of material, information and financial flows. Such a scheme of interaction ensures the effective functioning of the enterprise's business processes and creates conditions for the natural improvement of its organizational structure. The need to study logistics management processes, find the latest directions for improving logistics activities, develop methods of applying modern innovative tools, search for scientific and methodological recommendations with the application of innovations in the logistics sector, improve the organizational structure of innovative activities of the enterprise as the main element of the economic macro-environment, lead to the need to form a performance evaluation system innovative development of logistics activities.

Therefore, according to the conducted research, the author believes that the **system for assessing the effectiveness of the innovative development of logistics activity of a transport enterprise** is a set of interconnected elements that form a single whole thanks to

the qualitative measurement of the planned goals, performing actions aimed at ensuring the coordinated and effective execution of all stages of the logistics process, with the aim of transitioning to a new, higher level and obtaining greater performance of the transport enterprise.

In the context of assessing the effectiveness of the innovative development of a motor transport enterprise and a region in terms of sustainable development goals, various programmes can be used to model game situations between the enterprise and the region. This allows us to identify equilibrium strategies, optimise processes and choose the best solutions to ensure maximum economic effect, taking into account economic, institutional, technological, environmental and social aspects of sustainable development.

Several software languages and tools are used to find the Nash equilibrium, depending on the context and complexity of the problem. The main ones are:

1. Python: The most widely used language for economic and mathematical modelling due to libraries such as:

- Nashpy is a specialised library for computing Nash equilibrium in game theory.

- SciPy and NumPy - for working with matrices and numerical methods.

- Gambit is a Python API for analysing game theory, supporting various game solutions, including Nash equilibrium. Gambit: Specialised game analysis and Nash equilibrium software that supports various solution methods for games in normal and extended form. Gambit can be integrated with Python.

2. MATLAB: Suitable for calculating equilibrium in games with built-in functions for working with linear and nonlinear models. MATLAB is widely used in academic research due to its power in numerical calculations.

3. A language for statistics and modelling that also has packages for game theory, for example: "GameTheory" - a package for analysing strategic games, in particular for finding Nash equilibrium.

Each language and tool has its own advantages depending on what types of games are being analysed (e.g. games with two or more players, pure or mixed strategies).

A Python program for finding a Nash equilibrium can be written using the Numpy library and a specialised library for game theory - Nashpy. Below is an algorithm for finding a Nash equilibrium in a game with two players, in our case, a road transport company and a region with regard to achieving sustainable development goals (Fig. 1):

- We define payout matrices for each player.

- We use Nashpy methods to find the Nash equilibrium.

- It determines how many equilibrium situations (strategies) the game has with corresponding Pareto wins.

- The best strategy is selected from the identified strategies

Fig. 1 Algorithm for finding a Nash equilibrium in a two-player game (road transport company and region with regard to achieving sustainable development goals) (Developed by the author on the basis of the source [19])

The software also needs an interface. To create a simple graphical user interface (GUI), you can use the Tkinter library. An example of a possible GUI where users can enter payoff matrices and see the result of a Nash equilibrium is shown in Fig. 2.

Description of the GUI:

Window: The user enters payout matrices for each player in the form of two-dimensional arrays.

Button: When you click on the button, the program calculates the Nash equilibrium and displays the result in a dialogue box.

Possible messages: The application may also display error messages if incorrect data is entered.

```
python
import tkinter as tk
from tkinter import messagebox
import nashpy as nash
import numpy as np

# Функція для знаходження рівноваги Неша
def find_nash():
    try:
        # Введення матриць
        A = np.array(eval(entry_a.get()))
        B = np.array(eval(entry_b.get()))

        # Створення гри
        game = nash.Game(A, B)

        # Знаходження рівноваги Неша
        equilibria = list(game.support_enumeration())

        # Виведення результату
        result = "\n".join([str(eq) for eq in equilibria])
        messagebox.showinfo("Рівноваги Неша", result)
    except Exception as e:
        messagebox.showerror("Помилка", f"Помилка у введенні даних: {e}")

# Створення вікна
window = tk.Tk()
window.title("Знаходження рівноваги Неша")

# Введення матриць
tk.Label(window, text="Матриця виграшів для гравця 1 (наприклад, [[3, 1], [0, 2]]):").pack()
entry_a = tk.Entry(window)
entry_a.pack()

tk.Label(window, text="Матриця виграшів для гравця 2 (наприклад, [[3, 0], [1, 2]]):").pack()
entry_b = tk.Entry(window)
entry_b.pack()

# Кнопка для запуску пошуку
tk.Button(window, text="Знайти рівновагу Неша", command=find_nash).pack()

# Запуск програми
window.mainloop()
```

Fig. 2 Interface on Tkinter for calculating the optimal strategy of two players in the Nash equilibrium.
(Developed by the author on the basis of the source [20])

On the basis of the identified optimal strategies, an economic strategy for innovative development of the logistics activities of a motor transport enterprise engaged in freight transportation is built.

The concept of economic strategy to improve the effectiveness of innovative development of logistics activities of motor transport enterprises with consideration of the goals of sustainable development should include the following aspects:

1. Optimising logistics processes through digitalisation

- Use of transport management systems (TMS): these systems allow for more efficient route planning, reducing delivery times and fuel costs. This helps to reduce carbon emissions, which is in line with the goals of sustainable development in the context of environmental responsibility.

- Integration of artificial intelligence and big data analytics: using analytics to predict demand, optimise freight flows and minimise vehicle downtime helps to achieve greater economic efficiency and reduce negative environmental impact.

2. Implementation of innovative technologies to improve energy efficiency:

- The economic strategy should include upgrading vehicles and technologies to reduce energy consumption:

- Electrification of the fleet: switching to electric trucks or hybrid vehicles will reduce dependence on fossil fuels and CO₂ emissions. This is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals, in particular Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and Goal 13 (Combating Climate Change).

- Use of renewable energy sources: the introduction of charging stations for electric vehicles powered by solar or wind energy can significantly increase the company's resilience to energy price fluctuations and reduce its carbon footprint.

3. Development of human capital and innovation culture:

- Professional development programmes and training in innovative technologies: well-trained staff is essential for the effective use of digital solutions and the management of innovation processes. Training employees in the principles of sustainable development and the introduction of the latest technologies will help to increase productivity and environmental compliance.

- Involvement of specialists in innovation management and sustainable development: professional teams for innovation should include experts in the fields of ecology, change management and digitalisation.

4. Innovative logistics solutions and supply chain optimisation:

- Implementation of green logistics concepts: reducing energy consumption throughout the supply chain - from the factory to the end consumer - through more efficient inventory management and transport coordination. This includes reducing the number of empty runs and using trucks powered by alternative energy sources.

- Multimodal solutions: a combination of different modes of transport (rail, sea, road) reduces transportation costs and emissions. This contributes to the sustainable development of regions by reducing the environmental impact of transport.

5. Increasing competitiveness through innovation and partnerships:

- Collaboration with research institutions and innovative start-ups: cooperation with innovative companies to develop new logistics solutions and technologies.

- Investing in research and development (R&D): supporting innovative development by funding research in logistics and environmentally friendly technologies will contribute to the long-term sustainability strategy and improve the company's performance.

6. Monitoring and evaluation of implemented innovations:

- Implementation of indicators to measure environmental and economic efficiency: regular monitoring of costs, energy consumption, emissions reduction and cost-effectiveness of innovative solutions allows for timely strategy adjustments.

- Data analytics and forecasting: the use of modern technologies to analyse large amounts of data will allow businesses to better predict the efficiency of their logistics operations and assess their environmental impact.

Conclusions.

An economic strategy to improve the effectiveness of innovative development of logistics activities of road transport enterprises should be based on the principles of digitalisation, environmental responsibility, energy efficiency and human capital development. Implementation of such strategies will help enterprises remain competitive in the market while achieving sustainable development goals, such as reducing carbon emissions, saving energy and increasing social responsibility.

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